

Supporting Figure S1

Supporting figure S1

Co-expression of GFP-NtARPC2 with different organellar markers shows the exclusive association of ARP2/3 spots with the peroxisomes. Colocalization was observed in *Arabidopsis thaliana* hypocotyl epidermal cells (a, b, c, e, f) and in BY-2 tobacco suspension cells (d) expressing GFP-NtARPC2 with co-visualized organelles. (a-e) The ARP2/3 spots do not colocalize with ER, visualized by co-expressed ER-RFP marker (a, 1), plastids (b, autofluorescence), co-expressed GA-RFP marker (c, 1), mitochondria labeled by MitoTracker Red (d) or TGN, visualized by co-expressed RABD2A-RFP marker (e, 2). (f) ARP2/3 spots are exclusively associated with a subpopulation of peroxisomes, visualized by mCherry-PTS1 marker 1). Scale bars = 10 μm.

References:

1: Nelson BK, Cai X, Nebenführ A. A multicolored set of in vivo organelle markers for co-localization studies in *Arabidopsis* and other plants. *Plant J.* 2007 Sep;51(6):1126-36. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2007.03212.x.

2: Geldner N, Dénervaud-Tendon V, Hyman DL, Mayer U, Stierhof YD, Chory J. Rapid, combinatorial analysis of membrane compartments in intact plants with a multicolor marker set. *Plant J.* 2009 Jul;59(1):169-78. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2009.03851.x.

Supporting Figure S2

Supporting figure S2

GFP-NtARPC2 and GFP-AtARPC2 motile spots colocalize with peroxisomes in stably expressing BY-2 cells (a) and transiently transformed tobacco leaf pavement cells (b). (c-e) motile spots formed by inducible GFP-NtARPC2 were observed under conditions of very low protein expression (d, 2 nM β -estradiol, compare with e, 2 μ M β -estradiol), while no signal was observed in uninduced controls (c). (f) Detection of GFP-NtARPC2 in Western blots demonstrates the expression levels of the GFP-NtARPC2 subunit induced by 2 nM and 2 μ M β -estradiol in cells shown in (c-e). Note that 2 nM β -estradiol-induced cells have considerably lower expression, which is undetectable in 11 ng of total proteins loaded when compared to cells expressing under the 35S promoter or cells induced by 2 μ M β -estradiol. Beta-tubulin levels are shown as a control of protein loading, as well as Coomassie Brilliant Blue (CBB) staining below. Samples derive from the same experiment and gels/blots were processed in parallel. (g-k) The expression of GFP-fusion proteins rescued the phenotype of distorted trichomes of the *arp2/distorted2-1* (h) and *arp5* (j) mutant line. True leaves of mutants expressing respective fusion protein (i, k) resembled WT trichomes (g). (l-o) Variable angle epifluorescence microscopy (VAEM) of GFP-ARPC2 and GFP-ARPC5 in hypocotyls of *Arabidopsis* plants (see also Supporting Movie 2). (l) GFP-ARPC2 spots of various sizes. (m) Some peroxisomes showed weak peroxisomal lumen staining besides one signal maximum. (n) Exceptionally, entirely labeled peroxisome without signal maximum was observed in cell expression GFP-ARPC2. (o) Peroxisomal spots and cytosolic signal in GFP-ARPC2 expressing cells. (p) ARP2/3 subunits GFP-ARPC2 and ARPC5-mCherry, and ARP2/3 subunit ARPC5-mCherry and NAP1-GFP co-immunoprecipitate in extracts from *Arabidopsis* stably expressing respective markers. Black lines indicates re-arrangement of non adjacent lines. Scale bars: (a,b) = 2 μ m, (c-e) = 10 μ m, (g-k) = 200 μ m, (l-o) = 3 μ m.

Supporting Figure S3

Supporting figure S3

(a, b) Actin filaments marked by GFP-FABD in *Arabidopsis* cotyledons were completely depolymerized after 30 min of treatment with 500 nM latrunculin B. (c-e) Treatment with 40 mM oryzalin for 3 hours did not alter the structure or peroxisomal localization of ARP2/3 spots (c), although it dissolved the microtubular cytoskeleton completely (e, compared to untreated control in d). (f) Visualisation of actin filaments in fixed BY-2 cells using TRITC-phalloidin and imaged using VAEM. ARP2/3 peroxisomal domains represented by GFP-NtARPC2 (arrows) colocalize with actin filaments. Scale bars: 50 μm (a, b), 20 μm (c, d, e), 2 μm (f).

Supporting Figure S4

Supporting figure S4

(a) densitometry of anti-catalase bands on Western blots of protein extracts from WT, *arpc2*, and *arpc5* *Arabidopsis* in vitro grown plants, as measured in ImageJ from three technical replicates (b), indicates a higher abundance of peroxisomes in mutants ($p = 2.49e-04$, ANOVA, between-group differences were determined by Tukey test [$p = 3.52e-04$ for WT vs. *arpc2* and $5.68e-04$ for WT vs. *arpc5*], black bars indicate means). (c) N-BODIPY fluorescence of protein extracts from WT and ARP2/3 mutants indicate higher content of peroxisomes, similar to autophagy mutant *atg5*, used here as a positive control. For each variant $n = 18$ (three biological and six technical replicates for each sample), $p = 1.67e-07$ (ANOVA), between-group differences were determined by Tukey test. (d) ARP2/3 mutant lines *arpc4* and *arpc5* responded to IBA by increased initiation of lateral roots ($p = 6.42e-12$, GLM with Poisson distribution), indicating a functional β -oxidation pathway that converts IBA to auxin. There is not significant difference between the responses of WT and mutant lines ($p = 0.82$, GLM with Poisson distribution) Central lines indicate the mean, error bars indicate 95% CI, $n = 3$ for mock treatment of WT, *arpc4*, *arpc5* and IBA treatment of WT, and $n = 4$ for IBA treatment of *arpc4* and *arpc5*. (e,f) The degradation of storage oil bodies in ARP2/3 mutants was not significantly different when compared to WT ($p = 0.6478$, Beta regression, p -values in graphs indicate results of post-hoc comparison of group means). Area fraction occupied by oil bodies was calculated for confocal sections, $n = 20$ (WT), 19 (*arpc5*), 20 (non-induced *arpc2*:GFP-NtARPC2), 20 (induced *arpc2*:GFP-NtARPC2); 10 plants were analyzed in each variant. Central lines in boxplots represent the median. Scale bars in c = 20 μm . Graphs 4c and 4e are box plots with central line representing mean, box representing interquartile range (IQR), whiskers extending to minima and maxima, outliers larger than 1.5x IQR plotted separately.

Supporting Figure S5

Supporting figure S5

Variable angle epifluorescence microscopy (VAEM) reveals significantly more colocalization events between ARP2/3 spots and autophagosomes than confocal microscopy. The percentage of GFP-ARPC2 spots colocalized with RFP-ATG8f was analyzed from images obtained by LSCM on Leica SP8 and by VAEM on ZEISS Elyra SP.1. Both manual (M) and automated (A) analysis showed significantly higher colocalization in VAEM (quasibinomial GLM, $p = 2.70e-10$). There is no significant difference between results from automated and manual analysis ($p = 0.983$). For LSCM, $n = 157$, for VAEM (M), $n = 70$, for VAEM (A), $n = 57$. The graph shows individual data points and means with 95% confidence intervals and significance was estimated by a bootstrapping-based method. The automatic time series colocalization method and description, as well as the list of parameters used for the analysis, are included in Supplementary method S1.

Supporting Figure S6

Supporting figure S6

(a, b) Colocalization between GFP-NtARPC2 and RFP-ATG8f in VAEM (see also Supporting Movie 6). (a) peroxisome with one bright spot and weak signal in the peroxisomal lumen of GFP-NtARPC2. The bright ARP2/3 spot co-localizes with autophagosomal marker RFP-ATG8f. (b) GFP-NtARPC2 spot engulfed in the autophagosomal membrane. (c) Co-expression of peroxisome marker (CFP-PTS1) and autophagosomes (RFP-ATG8f) imaged in CLSM. This picture shows a rarely observed advanced pexophagy with the whole peroxisome engulfed by the autophagosomal membrane (right peroxisome) and a more frequently observed association of small autophagosome at the peroxisomal periphery (left peroxisome). Scale bars: (a,b) = 3 μ m, c = 5 μ m

Supporting Figure S7

Supporting figure S7

Treatment with 3-MA resulted in an increased number of both ARP2/3 spots (c-f) and peroxisomes (a-f) in both *Arabidopsis* (a-d) and BY-2 cells (e,f). 3-MA treatment resulted in an increased number of autophagosomes and also in a change in the RFP-ATG8f marker localization. Under control conditions, the ATG8f signal was localized mainly in the vacuole, and some ATG8f-labeled structures were found in the cytoplasm (a). After 3-MA treatment, the ATG8f marker was found mainly in the cytoplasm and nuclei (b). (b') is the enlarged inset in (b) showing co-localization of ATG8f bodies and peroxisomes. Scale bars = 20 μ m for a-f and 10 μ m for b' enlarged inset. (g) Autophagy flux after the treatment with NAA, 3-MA, CA (concanamycin A) and their combinations. (h-i) The increase of catalase (h) and ATG8 (i) in *Arabidopsis* plants treated with 10 mM 3-MA for three days measured as a density of catalase on the Western blot. Black lines indicates re-arrangement of non adjacent lines. (j) Autophagy flux in WT, *arpc2*, and *arpc5* mutants in a control medium or in a medium with concanamycin A (CA). Autophagy flux was expressed as a ratio of cleaved free RFP and full-length RFP-ATG8f.

Supporting Figure S8

Supporting figure S8

Colocalization of peroxisome-associated ARP2/3 spots with peroxisomal proteins. Transient expression in leaves of *N. benthamiana*. (a) mCherry-MCD1 colocalization with GFP-AtARPC2. (b) colocalization of GFP-SCO3 spot with peroxisomes, (c) colocalization of ARPC5-mCherry with GFP-SCO3, (d) colocalization of GFP-ChEC51 and (e) colocalization of GFP-ChEC96 with peroxisomes as spot-like structures, (f) colocalization of AtARPC5-mCherry with GFP-ChEC96. Scale bars = 10 μ m (a, c) 2 μ m (b), 5 μ m (d-f)

Blots from Supporting Figure S2a

rabbit anti-GFP 1:6000, anti-rabbit HRP ENZO 1:6000

rabbit anti-GFP 1:6000, anti-rabbit HRP ENZO 1:6000

mouse anti-alfatubulin TU01 1:4000, anti-mouse HRP ADI-SAB-100 1:10000

CBB staining

Blots from Supporting Figure S2p

Blots from Supporting Figure S4b

Blots from Supporting Figure S7

Fig. S7g

Fig. S7h

Fig. S7i

Fig. S7j

Supporting Table S1:

Consensus protein interactors of GFP-*Nt*ARPC2, identified in both repetitions of proteomic analysis.

Protein ID (Uniprot)	FASTA headers	PTS	intensity 1 (max. 26.3574)	intensity 2 (max. 26.1078)
A0A1S4DR85 A0A1S3ZA87	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit OS Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit OS		21.9136	23.7485
G0WLG3	Arp2/3 complex 34 kDa subunit OS		26.3574	26.1078
A0A1S3Z3H1 A0A1S3WXP2	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 3 OS Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 3 OS		21.5897	21.9216
A0A1S4BTZ8	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 4 OS		21.176	24.4566
A0A1S3ZCR5	Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 5 OS		21.4188	24.1816
A0A1S4DI60	actin-related protein 3 OS		21.5047	23.0667
A0A1S4A550 A0A1S4A514 A0A1S4A4Y5 A0A1S4A581	actin-related protein 3 isoform X4 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X3 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X2 OS actin-related protein 3 isoform X1 OS		19.7576	21.8903
A0A1S4A6H4	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	22.3573	22.0314
A0A1S4DNE8	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	20.9527	20.1321
A0A1S3XY53	peroxisomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein AIM1-like OS	PTS1	19.5933	22.0314
A0A1S4D439	LOW-QUALITY PROTEIN: glyoxysomal fatty acid beta-oxidation multifunctional protein MFP-a-like OS	PTS1	20.2187	19.6894
A0A1S4D6S9 A0A1S4D762 A0A1S4D720 A0A1S4A2D2	4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X3 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X2 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 isoform X1 OS 4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 6 OS	PTS1	21.3696	19.7423
A0A1S4AJ50	4-coumarate--CoA ligase-like 7 OS	PTS1	24.8577	22.5521
A0A1S4DHZ4 A0A1S4DQN6	probable quinone oxidoreductase OS probable quinone oxidoreductase OS	PTS1	24.2513	21.5504
A0A1S3Y9E9 A0A1S4D3Y8 A0A1S4ASM7 A0A1S3YQG6	Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS Aspartate aminotransferase OS	PTS2	23.703	20.0947
A0A1S3Z7C4 A0A1S3Z7V8	delta(3,5)-Delta(2,4)-dienoyl-CoA isomerase, peroxisomal isoform X1 OS delta(3,5)-Delta(2,4)-dienoyl-CoA isomerase, peroxisomal isoform X2 OS	PTS1	23.4051	21.0945
A0A1S3Y1Q5 A0A1S3YTH0	acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 13-like OS acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 13-like OS	PTS1	21.8947	18.5317
A0A1S3YP09	glyoxysomal processing protease, glyoxysomal-like OS	PTS1	24.5543	21.6784
A0A1S4BMM1 A0A1S3XIF9	gamma-glutamyl peptidase 5-like OS gamma-glutamyl peptidase 5-like OS		22.0176	19.499

Supporting Table S2

Primers used for cloning described constructs. Restriction sites overhangs in red.

gene	direction	restriction site	Sequence
ARPC2	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	GGATCCAATGATACTATTGCAGTCACATTC
	Reverse	<i>Hind</i> III	AAGCTTCTACTTCCGAGTTGGTGTGATTG
ARPC5 (GFP)	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	GGATCCAATGGCAGAATTCGTTGAAGCTG
	Reverse	<i>Hind</i> III	AAGCTTCAAACGGTGTGATGGTATCAGTAAG
ARPC5 (mCh)	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	AAAGGATCCATGGCAGAATTCGTTGAAG
	Reverse	<i>Xma</i> I	TTTCCCGGAACGGTGTGATGGTATCAG
MCD	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	AAAAAAGGATCCATGAGCAAGAAAAATCTAGCGATTC
	Reverse	<i>Eco</i> RI	AAAAAAGAATTCCTAGAGACGGGAATGGATAC

Supporting table S3

Parameters used for semi-automatic time series colocalization analysis for individual sample channels.

Experiment Sample (exp_plant)	Channel	Preprocessing			Trackmate parameters (particle tracking)							ComDet parameters (object colocalization)			
		Gaussian filter before tracking?	Gaussian filter radius (px)	Detector type	Particle radius (micron)	Quality threshold	Median filter?	Subpixel localization?	Tracker type	Max linking distance (micron)	Max gap closing distance (micron)	Max frame gap	Particle size (px)	Intensity threshold	Centroid max distance (px)
A_11	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	2000	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_11	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	1	2	1	12	1	15
A_12	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	350	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_12	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	175	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_13	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	550	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_13	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	350	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_14	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	950	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_14	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_22	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	850	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_22	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_23	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	175	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_23	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_24	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	75	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_24	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_31	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	75	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_31	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	400	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_32	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	75	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_32	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	500	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_33	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	125	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_33	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	475	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_34	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_34	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	600	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_35	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	50	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_35	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_36	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_36	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	600	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_41	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_41	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	350	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_42	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_42	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	450	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_43	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	75	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_43	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	650	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_44	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	475	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_44	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	250	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_53	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	30	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_53	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	9	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_54	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	20	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_54	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	90	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_55	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	20	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_55	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	400	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_56	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	30	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_56	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	425	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_57	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_57	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	550	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
A_58	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
A_58	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	2	2	12	1	15
B_11	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	125	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_11	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	130	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_12	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_12	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	2	12	1	15
B_13	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	600	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_13	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	3	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	2	12	1	15
B_14	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	700	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_14	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	350	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	2	12	1	15
B_15	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_15	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	400	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	2	12	1	15
B_21	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	1500	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_21	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	450	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_22	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	2000	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_22	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	600	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_23	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	900	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_23	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	850	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_24	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	900	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_24	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	550	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_25	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	900	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_25	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	1200	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_31	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	600	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_31	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	450	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_32	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_32	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	375	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	12	1	15
B_33	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	30	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_33	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	200	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_34	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_34	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	300	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_35	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	30	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_35	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	12	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_36	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_36	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_41	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_41	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	425	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_42	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	20	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_42	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	1150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_43	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	20	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_43	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_44	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
B_44	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.3	1100	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
B_45	green	FALSE	NA	LoG	0.2	20	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	8	1	15
B_45	red	TRUE	2	LoG	0.35	125	TRUE	FALSE	Simple LAP	1	1	1	12	1	15
C_11	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_11	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	740	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_11	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	475	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_13	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	700	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_13	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	500	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_15	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_15	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	500	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_16	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	150	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_16	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	650	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_17	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_17	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_18	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	80	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_18	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	300	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_19	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	450	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_19	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	375	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_22	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	100	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	8	1	15
C_22	red	TRUE	2	DoG	0.35	800	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2.5	1.5	1	12	1	15
C_23	green	FALSE	NA	DoG	0.25	200	FALSE	FALSE	Simple LAP	2	1	1	8	1	15

Supplementary method S1

Time series colocalization - from supporting figure S5

Image acquisition for object-based colocalization

TIRF microscopy was performed using the Zeiss ELYRA PS.1 imaging system on 6-8-day old *Arabidopsis thaliana* hypocotyl epidermal cells with the alpha Plan-Apochromat objective 100x Oil DIC M27 Elyra (NA 1.46, WD 0.11 mm) equipped with sCMOS PCO Edge 5.5 camera. Zeiss Immersol 518 F for 30°C was used as immersion media (RI 1.518). HILO mode was used. Images were acquired in two channels: ARPC2-GFP and RFP-ATG8f were excited at 488 nm (HR Diode 488-300) and 561 nm (HR DPSS 561-200), respectively, at a 1% strength. Emission was collected using the filter set LBF 488/561.

Image restoration

Image analysis was carried out in 1280x1280 pixel squared sections along the x-y axis. The collected images were initially corrected for crosstalk using the built-in Huygens Professional Crosstalk Corrector with default parameters, including noise reduction. The Deconvolution Wizard built into Huygens Professional was then used to do sequential deconvolution on each channel of the corrected pictures, with a maximum of 50 iterations using the default CMLE (Classic Maximum Likelihood Estimate). The confocal deconvolution option was used with the theoretical PSF (Point Spread Function) and NA (Numerical Aperture) set to 1.46. Each image channel's background was chosen manually in accordance with Huygens Professional recommendations. The remaining settings were all left at default. Huygens Professional version 22.10.0p3 64b was used.

Particle detection, tracking, and object-based colocalization

The popular ImageJ TrackMate plugin (Tinevez et al. 2016) was used to process each restored image independently for spot identification and tracking using the particle detection and tracking algorithms with the parameters listed below. A label image and a table with the detected spot centroids and their track grouping were obtained for each image channel.

Subsequently, dots found in autofluorescence zones were discarded via a customized ImageJ macro (see below). Briefly, Renyi's Entropy approach was used to automatically threshold bright autofluorescence regions on the original images. After particle filtering, which kept only objects larger than $5\mu\text{m}^2$, dots inside the thresholded regions were identified as autofluorescence and discarded for any further investigation. The ImageJ plugin ComDet (Katrukha et al. 2022) was employed to perform object-based colocalization analysis for individual timeframes in label pictures, with particles deemed to colocalize if their centroids were within 15 pixels of each other.

To count individual colocalization events throughout time series for particles that persisted for at least three frames, the resulting colocalization data was combined with tracking data and filtered using a customized Python script (see below).

1. Jean-Yves Tinevez, Nick Perry, Johannes Schindelin, Genevieve M. Hoopes, Gregory D. Reynolds, Emmanuel Laplantine, Sebastian Y. Bednarek, Spencer L. Shorte, Kevin W. Eliceiri, **TrackMate: An open and extensible platform for single-particle tracking**, *Methods*, Available online 3 October 2016, ISSN 1046-2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2016.09.016>.

2. Katrukha, E. **ekatrukha/ComDet: ComDet 0.5.5**. (2022) [doi:10.5281/zenodo.6546038](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6546038).

The script detailed description is available here:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7709848>

Supplementary method S2

for nLC-MS² analysis from supporting table S1

Protein Digestion

IP samples were resuspended in 100mM TEAB containing 2% SDC. Cysteines were reduced with 5mM final concentration of TCEP (60 °C for 60 min) and blocked with 10mM final concentration of MMTS (10 min Room Temperature). Samples were cleaved on beads with 1 µg of trypsin at 37 °C overnight. After digestion, samples were centrifuged and supernatants were collected and acidified with TFA to 1% final concentration. SDC was removed by extraction to ethyl acetate (Masuda *et al.*, 2008). Peptides were desalted on the Michrom C18 column.

nLC-MS² Analysis

Nano Reversed phase column (EASY-Spray column, 50 cm x 75 µm ID, PepMap C18, 2 µm particles, 100 Å pore size) was used for LC/MS analysis. Mobile phase buffer A was consisting of water and 0.1% formic acid. Mobile phase B was consisting of acetonitrile and 0.1% formic acid. Samples were loaded onto the trap column (Acclaim PepMap300, C18, 5 µm, 300 Å Wide Pore, 300 µm x 5 mm, 5 Cartridges) for 4 min at 15 µl/min. Loading buffer was consisting of water, 2% acetonitrile and 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid. Peptides were eluted with Mobile phase B gradient from 4% to 35% B in 60 min. Eluting peptide cations were converted to gas-phase ions by electrospray ionization and analyzed on a Thermo Orbitrap Fusion (Q-OT-qIT, Thermo). Survey scans of peptide precursors from 400 to 1600 m/z were performed at 120K resolution (at 200 m/z) with a 5×10^5 ion count target. Tandem MS was performed by isolation at 1.5 Th with the quadrupole, HCD fragmentation with a normalized collision energy of 30, and rapid scan MS analysis in the ion trap. The MS² ion count target was set to 10^4 and the max injection time was 35 ms. Only those precursors with charge state 2–6 were sampled for MS². The dynamic exclusion duration was set to 45 s with a 10ppm tolerance around the selected precursor and its isotopes. Monoisotopic precursor selection was turned on. The instrument was run in top speed mode with 2 s cycles (Hebert *et al.*, 2014).

All data were analyzed and quantified with the MaxQuant software (version 1.5.3.8) (Cox *et al.*, 2014). The false discovery rate (FDR) was set to 1% for both proteins and peptides and we specified a minimum length of seven amino acids. The Andromeda search engine was used for the MS/MS spectra search against the *Arabidopsis thaliana* database (downloaded from Uniprot on July 2016, containing 51 445 entries). Enzyme specificity was set as C-terminal to Arg and Lys, also allowing cleavage at proline bonds and a maximum of two missed cleavages. Dithiomethylation of cysteine was selected as fixed modification and N-terminal protein acetylation and methionine oxidation as variable modifications. The “match between runs” feature of MaxQuant was used to transfer identifications to other LC-MS/MS runs based on their masses and retention time (maximum deviation 0.7 min) and this was also used in quantification experiments. Quantifications were performed with the label-free algorithms described recently. Data analysis was performed using Perseus 1.5.2.4 software